

Evaluation of Mechanical Properties of Extruded Ni-Al Bronze deposited over Cast Ni-Al Bronze by Friction Surfacing Method

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Abstract – The coating technology is mainly used for the corrosion protection method and long-term performance of parts. Presently there is a strong emphasis on the development of advanced functional coating techniques used in different applications. The main motivation for this study is to build know how on using the technology for surface coating due to the multiple industrial applications along with the fine equiaxed grains and good thickness presented by the coatings. These provide the needed properties to make Friction surfacing a suitable technique to produce coatings and to repair worn parts. Cast nickel-aluminum bronze (NAB) alloy is specified for many marine applications, including ship propellers, due to its excellent corrosion-resistance combined with acceptable mechanical properties. Extruded nickel aluminum bronze was deposited over cast nickel aluminum bronze by friction surfacing. In the present work the corrosion properties and mechanical properties of coated nickel aluminum bronze was studied and found that corrosion resistance and mechanical properties gets increased when compared with the uncoated nickel aluminum bronze due to grain refinement.

Keywords: Wind Surface coating, Corrosion Properties, Ni-Al Bronze

I. Introduction

Surface engineering has become a very important field of research in the last few years. Wear, corrosion and fatigue are the primary reason for the failure of most components, because, these events occurs at the surface. The surface failures requires large sum for repair or unscheduled stop and also needs extensive expertise, momentous resources to control [1]. One of the surface engineering techniques is friction surfacing. Friction Surfacing (FS) is a well established technology to produce coating, repair worn parts or manufacture functionally graded materials (FGM's)[2]. Friction Surfacing process (FSP) is applied to cast metals, FSP can eliminate casting defects such as porosity and improve the mechanical properties[4]. FSP utilizes consumable cylindrical tool (mechtrode) with a concentric pin at one end. The mechtrode is rotated and pressed into a material surface and a combination of frictional and adiabatic heating softens the material, while simultaneously exposing it to a stirring action, resulting in homogenous mixing and refined grain structures. Cast Nickel Aluminum Bronze (NAB) for marine applications have earned it the nickname 'propeller bronze'. It exhibits a unique combination of properties including moderate strength and toughness, excellent fatigue strength, corrosion, cavitations, and erosion resistance, which make it an outstanding choice of material for use as naval propellers. These bronzes are Copper based alloys with addition [6-7]. It was shown that the achieved homogeneity and the fine grained microstructure are advantageous for the mechanical

properties of the bronze, and that small voids and casting defects near the surface can be closed [8-9]. The above described methods are not applicable for larger casting defects as well as worn or damaged surfaces where new material has to be added. Standard fusion welding methods have up to now been employed for repairing components, if at all possible. Adequate mechanical properties can be achieved, but typical additional measures, e.g. subsequent heat treatment and non destructive testing to detect welding defects, are necessary [10,11]. For such cases, friction surfacing could be a useful alternative, since it allows depositing material which immediately possesses a favorable microstructure. The possibility of welding under water could be an additional gain [12]. From the literature review, very few published information is available on corrosion performance and mechanical behavior of friction surfaced coatings in NAB, the corrosion behavior and mechanical behavior of the material in various forms has been widely studied because of its industrial significance. The Principle working of Friction stir surfacing method is illustrated in the Fig 1.

Fig. 1 Principle of Friction surfacing

II. Materials and Experimental Methods

Friction surfacing was performed with studs of 20 mm diameter and 70 mm length, on plates having dimensions of 150 mm×150 mm×10 mm. Chemical composition of cast substrate and mechtrode material are shown in Table 1. The substrate was prepared for surfacing by grinding with 120- grit abrasive paper and degreasing with acetone. A fully computer numerical controlled (CNC) friction stir welding (FSW) machine was used to perform the coating. Surfacing parameters were 200 mm/min traverse speed, 60 mm/min plunge rate and a rotational speed of the studs of 2500 rpm. Single layer surfacing has been performed. The coating produced by the friction surfacing sample of deposition stage and coating is shown in Fig.1

TABLE I
CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF CAST SUBSTRATE

Element	Cu	Al	Ni	Fe	Mn	Si
Substrate	81.6	10.10	3.78	4.01	0.30	0.16 (max)
Mechtrode	80.9	10.20	3.77	4.6	0.27	0.17

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2 (a) Friction Stir Processing area (b) Surfacing in Ni-Al Bronze

II.1. Tensile Testing

Tensile test were performed using Universal Testing Machine with a 100KN load the sample preparation should be according to the ASTM E8-08 standard. The parent metal and coated samples are machined to the dimensions shown in Fig 2. Machined samples are shown.

Fig 3.(a) Parent material specimen,(b) Friction surfaced Tensile specimen

II.2. Corrosion Properties

Salt spray test were performed in a salt spray test apparatus as shown in Fig 4. Specimens are first cut to the size as specified by as per ASTM B117M (Salt Spray fog test). Holes are drilled at the top of each specimen so that they could be held steadily as shown in Fig 5. The weight of the individual specimens is noted before the test starts. The chamber has a provision at the side for spraying NaCl. Sodium chloride is sprayed in the form of fine droplets similar to fog. It is sprayed for about 24, 48 and 72 hours. For each 24 hours one parent metal and one coated specimen are taken out. It should be repeated for 48 hrs. and 72 hrs. Following which specimen is carefully removed and washed with distilled water and concentrated HCL in the ratio of 2:1. After residues are dissolved it is once again weighed. Comparison of weights before and after the test was calculated and evaluated.

Fig. 4 Salt spray chamber

II.3. Salt Spray Parameters

- Temperature of the test: 33 °C

- Concentration of the Salt solution: 1.0M
- Air pressure: 2.0 Kg per Sq. Centimeters
- PH of the solution followed: 7.0.
- Exposure Time: 24, 48 and 72 Hours.
- Post-cleaning: Cleaned in distilled water with concentrated HCL

Fig. 5 Ni-Al Corrosion Tested samples (a) Parent Samples (b) Deposited Samples

TABLE II
WEIGHT LOSS AND CORROSION RATE OF PARENT SAMPLES

Spraying time for Parent metal	24 hours	48 hours	72 hours
Initial weight	2.14	3.23	3.08
Final weight	2.14	3.22	3.07
Weight loss(g)	0.03	0.86	0.16
Corrosion rate (mm/yr)	0.08	1.17	1.49

TABLE III
WEIGHT LOSS AND CORROSION RATE OF DEPOSITED SAMPLES

Spraying time for Deposited metal	24 hours	48 hours	72 hours
Initial weight(g)	4.0462	8.2905	3.9851
Final weight(g)	4.0460	8.2844	3.9718
Weight loss(g)	0.0002	0.0061	0.0133
Corrosion rate (mm/yr)	0.0544	0.8301	1.2066

Fig. 6 Spraying Time vs Corrosion rate

II.4. Optical Microstructure

The optical micrographs of the substrate (cast NAB), mechtrode (Extruded NAB) and friction surfaced interface zone. The cast NAB material has a dual phase structure which contains marten site and α phase. Tool material shows (Mechatrode) Widmanstätten pattern of microstructure. The microstructure within one coating layer contains lamellar as well as globular α grains, surrounded by quenched β phase. Close to the surface of the layer, the phase is of lamellar shape.

Fig. 7 Microstructure samples of NI-Al Bronze (a) Parent material (b) Friction surfaced structure after salt spray test

III. Results and Discussion

Grain boundary strengthening is given by the hall patch relation $\sigma_y = \sigma_0 + k/\sqrt{d}$ where σ_y is the yield strength, k is the strengthening coefficient, d is the grain diameter,

σ_0 is a materials constant for the starting stress for dislocation movement for copper alloys $\sigma_0=25\text{Mpa}, k=0.11 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, so according to hall petch relation when the grain size get smaller yield strength get increases since the coated metal have finer grain size as its strength get increases than the parent metal. First, the coarse microstructure of the NAB as shown in (fig 7) had a lower corrosion resistance than the finer counterpart

The coarser microstructures resulted in a deeper attack. They resulted in the segregation of elements especially in the grain boundaries and this could provide the corrosion path for the solution of preferentially corroded phases. FSP resulted in the breakup/decomposition of the coarse phases and the homogenization of elements as shown in (fig 9) This greatly eliminated the corrosion path, thereby enhancing the corrosion resistance [14]. Secondly, the cast porosities in the cast sample provided shortcuts for corrosion. On the one hand, these regions showed much lower corrosion resistance than the densified regions. On the other hand, the porosities increased the area between the sample and the corrosion solution and this further accelerated the corrosion process [15].

However FSP eliminated the porosities, and therefore increased the corrosion resistance effectively. The influence of spraying time on corrosion morphology of the specimen sprayed in NaCl solution of pH 7 with different spraying time of 24, 48 and 72 hour

The increase in the spraying time enhances the corrosion products which accumulated over the surface of the samples. This is attributed to the corrosion occurring over an increasing fraction of the surface, which is the soluble corrosion product. The soluble corrosion product on the surface of the alloy could increase the corrosion rate.

IV. Conclusion

The tensile strength increases in coated metal compared with the parent metal this is due to fine equiaxed homogeneous distributed grains formed due to friction surfacing. The coated metal exhibits low corrosion rate and mass loss compared with the parent metal. The corrosion rate was increased with increase in spraying time.

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